

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style and guidelines:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or with small-scale studies in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row)
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example 60 kg N ha; not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number for example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure spell out in full the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were . . . or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in . . .
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or some numbers higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia
- Write out all numbers that start sentences For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible equipment
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should have quantified data (%infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Fertility restorers for cytosterile stocks

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The discovery of an effective cytoplasmic genetic male sterility system led to successful hybrid rice development in China. Identification of restorer genotypes to ensure fertility restoration in F_1 hybrids produced with cytogenetic male sterile (cms) stocks is important.

Standard varieties, cultures in advanced evaluation stages, and elite breed-

ing lines entered in the International Rice Observational Nursery, International Rice Yield Nurseries, and National Evaluation Trials were screened to identify fertility restorers that could be used in F_1 hybrid production. Growth duration of genotypes used as pollinators was less than 135 days. The common female parent for pollinators was cms V.20A. Hybrids were produced by hand pollinating cms stock. F_1 hybrids were grown in a test cross nursery and evaluated for pollen fertility and percent seed set. Pollen fertility was determined by cytologic-

Restorers and maintainers for WA cytosterile stocks identified at CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Effective restorers	Partial or weak restorers	Maintainers (nonrestorers)
	<i>Varieties</i>	
PR106	Jaya	Madhu
PR107	Prakash	Karikalan
Mahsuri	Akash	MW 10
Archana	Amarnath	Kaveri
Jamuna	Parijatha	Gaur-I
N22	Kumar	C-22
	Kalinga II	
	Ratna	
	Rasi	
	Triveni	
	Kranthi	
	<i>Advanced cultures</i>	
IET2815	IET4141	
IET6314	IET6148	
IET6983		
IET6721		
	<i>Elite breeding lines</i>	
CRI29-118	BR109-74-2-2-1	Rasht 545
BR40-178-2-1	BR319-1	BW-242-5-5
BR171-213-8	AD7486	ES3-17-164
BIET360	RP825-28-7-1	KAU-1675
BKN7033-13-1-1-3-2	RP975-26-4-7-1	WGL-26420
UPRI03-80-1-2-1-2	RP1017-169-1-4	IR129-209-2-2-2-3
IR8455-78-1-3-3	RP8205-45-1-3	IR9761-40-3-2
IR8608-125-3-3	R35-2750	IR13240-39-3
IR9129-457-2-2-1-2	B733C-167-3-2	IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2
IR9224-73-2-2-2-3	MR136-1	IR19743-46-2-3
IR9698-16-3-3-2	KAU1924	IR19764-15-1-1
IR9761-19-1	TNAU17005	IR19819-31-2-3
IR9784-142-1-3-3	IR129-209-2-2-2-3	IR21931-67
IR13204-3-3-3-2	IR2071-586-5-6	
IR13429-109-2-2-1	IR3475-G2CO-CNT-84-1-1	
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	IR9209-26-2-2-2-3	
IR15529-256-1	IR9710-98-2	
	IR13427-45-3-1-2	
	IR13540-56-3-2-1	
	IR15314-43-2-3-3	
	IR15496-219-2-3	

al examination of pollen grains stained with I-KI solution. Percent seed set under self-pollination was evaluated by bagging the main panicles of the hybrid plants.

The pollinators were classified as: effective restorers, where fertility resto-

ration was above 80%; weak restorers or integrades where fertility restoration was 20-80%; and maintainers (nonrestorers) where fertility restoration was less than 10% (see table).

The effective restorers are being used

to produce F_1 hybrids for evaluating heterosis and combining ability. A recurrent backcross that uses maintainers to transfer the genome into wild aborted (WA) cytoplasm for developing additional cms stocks is in progress. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

IET6148, a variety for direct seeding

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Very early-maturing rice varieties were evaluated for direct seeding as part of the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement

Project Uniform Variety Trial I. Seed was soaked for 12 h and broadcast in puddled, leveled soil at 110 kg/ha. Water was carefully controlled for 1 week and then the crop was regularly irrigated. Trials were conducted in both kharif and rabi.

Cauvery and Tellahamsa, a popular short-duration high yielding variety, were checks. IET6148, 6149, 5860, 6155, 5858,4106,4107, and 6233 have been

evaluated since 1979 kharif.

IET6148, a progeny of Bala/Co 13, developed at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, gave consistently high (5.8 t/ha) yields. During 1979 kharif IET6148 was superior to all entries and yielded 6.2 t/ha. In 1980 kharif and 1981 rabi it yielded 5.9 and 6.1 t/ha, equal with Tellahamsa. ET6148 flowers in 75 days and has short bold grain. □

Govind, an early-maturing rice variety

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Govind, an early-maturing variety developed from the cross IR20/IR24, was recently released in Uttar Pradesh for general cultivation. Govind is a semidwarf (90 cm) variety that can be direct-seeded in rainfed fields or transplanted. It has 95- to 109-day maturity when direct-seeded in rainfed fields and 105-110 days when transplanted. Grains are long, slender, and translucent with good cooking quality and intermediate amylose content (23%).

Govind has been tested throughout Uttar Pradesh and in All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) trials for 5 years. Its performance in the AICRIP uniform variety trials is given in Table 1. Performance in the upland direct-seeded standard varietal trials and station trials (transplanting) is given in Tables 2 and 3.

Govind resists bacterial leaf blight, leaf blast, and brown leaf spot diseases and is moderately resistant to planthop-

Table 1. Performance of Govind in AICRIP trials when direct-seeded in upland rainfed fields.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Average	Days to 50% flowering (1980)
	1979 (mean of 23 locations)	1980 (mean of 31 locations)	1981 (mean of 17 locations)		
Govind	3.3	3.4	3.1	3.3	75
Bala	3.2	—	—	3.2	—
Cauvery	2.9	2.8	2.3	2.7	74
Akashi	—	2.8	—	2.8	69
Local check	3.4	3.3	2.5	3.1	75

Table 2. Performance of Govind in standard varietal trials in U.P. when direct-seeded in upland rainfed field.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Average	Days to maturity (1981)
	1980 (mean of 7 locations)	1981 (mean of 6 locations)			
Govind	2.1	2.5		2.3	96
Cauvery	2.1 ^a	2.0		2.1	98
N22	1.4	1.8		1.6	87

^a 5 locations only.

Table 3. Performance of Govind in U.P. when transplanted in station trials.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Average	Days to 50% flowering (1980)
	1979 (mean of 6 locations)	1980 (mean of 9 locations)			
Govind	5.1	3.9		4.5	81
Saket 4	5.1	4.4		4.7	87